

Direct Air Capture: Shining Knights or Useful Fools?

Martin Jukes, November, 2025.

Direct Air Capture (DAC) is the name given to the process of engineered extraction of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. In a scenario which involves atmospheric concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) going above safe levels, which now seems virtually unavoidable, many hope that DAC will give us the capability to draw CO₂ out of the atmosphere and bring the climate back into a safety zone.

DAC is not the only option. It is also possible to extract CO₂ from the atmosphere through biological processes, but the capacity for additional extraction for this route is questionable given the huge strain and over-demand already being placed on the biosphere. Advocates of DAC point to the fact that it can be scaled up without encountering the land-use limitations of biosphere methods. If driven by clean renewable power supplies, can provide a scalable mechanism to stabilise and reduce atmospheric burdens of greenhouse gasses.

On the downside, it has been suggested that DAC companies are acting as a fig-leave to provide excuses for companies which are postponing essential steps to reduce emissions. This interpretation is backed by a direct quote from Vicki Hollub, CEO of Occidental Petroleum, a company which is investing £1 billion in a new DAC facility in Texas (as reported by Politico, 2023¹). As noted in the Politico report, this is a shift into climate tech but not yet a shift away from fossil fuel: rather, the shift into climate tech is being seen as an alternative to deep emissions cuts.

We can also see those outside the oil industry being influenced by the positive energy associated with a proposed solution: the web pages for a 2022 IEA Technology Report refer to a “plan” by the US company 1pt5 to build 100 DAC sites by 2035, but the company itself has only got as far as announcing a scenario which includes 100 sites (1PointFive, 2023), and this ambition does not appear in the IEA report itself.. It is not clear whether the scenario has been published. The press release on this topic published by Carbon Brief (Carbon Brief, 2023) carries an explanatory footnote about “forward-looking statements” noting that they only represent views held at the time of the publication of the statements and do not necessarily reflect current plans. The

1 “This gives our industry a license to continue to operate for the 60, 70, 80 years that I think it’s going to be very much needed.” Vicki Hollub, CERWeek Conference, Houston, 2023.

figure cited by the IEA has, however, been cited in the peer review literature by Chen et al (2025).

A more balanced academic assessment is given by Chen et al. 2025. They note that DAC plants require “0.4 – 66.0 km² land for each ton of captured CO₂, much smaller than 862 km² required for the afforestation and reforestation to capture a similar amount of CO₂”. The large range of values reflects the huge uncertainty in this technology. Chen et al. also note that DAC becomes very inefficient if powered by gas-generated electricity.

Herzog et al. Criticise the use of “assumptions that are overly optimistic regarding the cost and scaling-up of DAC systems”, particularly with regard to the cost of electrical power and the capital costs of the infrastructure. They estimate costs in the range of \$263 to \$1,069 per ton of CO₂ removed and stored (i.e. for Direct Air Capture and Carbon Storage: DACCS). The low end of this range requires falling prices for electricity: this remains a possibility, but the need for rapid expansion in renewable energy supply could push up costs (e.g. replacing existing fossil fuel generation capacity before end-of-life pushes up costs).

Casaban et al. (2023) look at the feasibility of siting DAC plants in the Republic of Ireland. They note that projections for future efficiency gains depend on the emergence of new technologies or novel sorbents to draw CO₂ out of the atmosphere (the leading technology relies on sorbents which absorb CO₂ and can release it in a concentrated form when heated). Borchers et al. (2023) provide a similar analysis for Germany, reviewing all removal options and arriving at a price range of up to \$800 per ton for a DAC based approach.

Conclusion

Direct Air Capture is both an essential element of any realistic net zero plan and also being used by many as an excuse for actions which undermine progress towards net zero.

At the upper cost estimate, using DACCS to balance emissions for a return flight to New York from London Heathrow could add \$2,000 to the cost of the flight.

It is clear that such high offsetting costs would lead many to change their patterns of resource usage.

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